

THE POTENTIAL OF MACHINE LEARNING IN CYBERSECURITY

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Annotation: It is challenging to identify advantages in implementing and making decisions utilizing machine learning in cybersecurity because of the plethora of options that these advancements in the sector create. Also, attackers can target computer systems with the use of these technologies. In this paper, machine learning's application to cybersecurity and cyberattacks have been discussed.

Keywords: cyberattack, cybersecurity, machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), cyberattack based on machine learning.

Аннотация: Трудно определить преимущества при внедрении и принятии решений с использованием машинного обучения в сфере кибербезопасности из-за множества вариантов, которые создают эти достижения в этом секторе. Кроме того, с помощью этих технологий злоумышленники могут атаковать компьютерные системы. В этой статье рассматривается применение машинного обучения для кибербезопасности и кибератак.

Ключевые слова: кибератака, кибербезопасность, машинное обучение (МО), глубинное обучение (ГО), кибератака на основе машинного обучения.

INTRODUCTION

Cybersecurity is gaining more and more attention every year. The number of cyberattacks has increased significantly since 2009 due to the digitalization of

everything in the modern world. Machine learning (ML) is of great interest in the technology world. ML is concerned with intelligent behavior in a system, including perception, reasoning, learning, communication and action in a complex environment [1]. This widespread interest in ML is driven by two critical factors:

- firstly, MO can automate processes that previously required human participation, for example, controlling robotic mechanisms in production (that is, MO takes on human responsibilities);
- secondly, the ability to quickly process and analyze huge amounts of information and calculate options using many variables. In these areas, machine learning produces qualitatively better results compared to humans.

The process by which machines learn to construct logic and forecast outcomes based on provided data is known as machine learning [2]. Supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning are the three subcategories of machine learning [3]. A dataset with the correct answers labeled is used in supervised learning. These labels specify each data set's attributes. After the model has been trained, it can start predicting or making choices depending on fresh data. Such a labeled dataset is not needed during the unsupervised training phase. The program automatically creates clusters within a data collection by looking for patterns and relationships. But this kind of learning is not able to make any predictions.

Deep learning (DL) is a class of ML algorithms that uses multiple layers to gradually extract higher-level features from raw input data [4]. The main differences between ML and DL are: ML algorithms almost always require structured data, while DL networks rely on layers of artificial neural networks (ANNs).

RESULTS OF MODERN METHODS IN ELIMINATING CYBERATTACKS USING MACHINE LEARNING

The problem of using machine learning in cybersecurity is difficult to solve as advances in this field open up many opportunities, making it difficult to find good and profitable use cases for implementation and decision making. Moreover, it is difficult to determine how secure the security system used in production is and how to protect the organization from cyberattacks carried out through the DoD. The scope of ML in cybersecurity is vast, from identifying anomalies and suspicious or unusual behavior to detecting and patching zero-day vulnerabilities (Figure 1).

Figure 1. ML algorithms used in different types of attacks

The majority of ML and DL methods, including decision trees, ensemble learning, and clustering, are employed to find abnormalities, abuse, and hybrid cyberattacks. According to Evgeny Kaspersky’s official blog, Kaspersky uses machine learning to identify 99% of online dangers. Less than eight minutes are needed to identify questionable activity on a secured device [6]. DARPA and BAE Systems have created a system that sets up sensors and put safety precautions in place ‘at machine speed’. Known as ‘The CHASE program’ (acronym for Cyber Hunting at Scale), this endeavor seeks to create automated instruments for identifying current assaults, characterizing novel attacks, gathering pertinent contextual information, and dispersing preventive actions throughout business units [7]. Information collected from social media can help predict hacking attempts using neuro-linguistic programming and ML techniques. In Table 1, frequently used ML and DL algorithms in cybersecurity have been provided. Each of them has own advantages and disadvantages in preventing cyberattacks depending on types of threats.

Table 1. Popular ML and DL algorithms used in cybersecurity

Method	Working principal	Advantages	Disadvantages
Decision Tree	A rule-based tree-structured classification model, trained on	Computational cost is less and easy to implement.	Need to save all the information of the trained model. Space

	the basis of information gain of all features in training data		complexity is high.
Naive Bayes (NB) classifier	Calculates posterior probability of a class given inputs based on Bayes' rule	Robust to noisy training data, easy to implement, performance does not degrade with low sample size	Assumes all features contribute independently during the learning algorithm, but in practice this hardly happens
k-means clustering	Makes clusters or groups among training data points based on similarity measures	Easy to implement. Suitable for problems where labeling data is very difficult	Selecting k-value at the beginning requires domain knowledge
Recurrent neural network (RNN)	Processes sequential data integrating the temporal layer	Shows excellent performance for sequential data analysis, such as speech text	Vanishing or exploding gradient is the main disadvantage of the RNN
Restricted Boltzmann machine (RBM)	Unsupervised generative learning model, restricts the connection between nodes of the same layer (i.e., visible layer and hidden layer)	Feedback mechanism allows the RBM to extract important features in an unsupervised learning environment	Computational cost is very high
Deep belief network (DBN)	The DBN comprises stacked	The DBN shows better	Computational cost is very high

	RBM that execute greedy layer-by-layer training to get robust performance	performance than the RBM as it takes the RBM on the top of each layer of its training data	as it takes a high number of parameters
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CONCLUSION

To sum up, the incorporation of machine learning (ML) into cybersecurity poses a unique blend of prospects and difficulties never seen before. By evaluating enormous volumes of data in real-time, seeing trends, and forecasting future cyberattacks, machine learning algorithms hold the potential to improve threat detection and response capabilities. Unfortunately, the quality and diversity of the data used to train machine learning models determines how effective the models are, leaving them vulnerable to biases and adversarial attacks. To keep ahead of sophisticated attackers, machine learning approaches must also be continuously adjusted and refined due to the rapid growth of cyber threats.

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